

InDistill: Information flow-preserving knowledge distillation for model compression

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Abstract

In this paper, we introduce *InDistill*, a method that serves as a warmup stage for enhancing Knowledge Distillation (KD) effectiveness. *InDistill* focuses on transferring critical information flow paths from a heavyweight teacher to a lightweight student. This is achieved through a curriculum learning-based training scheme that considers the distillation difficulty of each layer and the critical learning periods when the information flow paths are established. This procedure can lead to a student model that is better prepared to learn from the teacher. To ensure the applicability of *InDistill* across a wide range of teacher-student pairs, we also incorporate a pruning operation when there is a discrepancy in the width of the teacher and student layers. This pruning operation reduces the width of the teacher’s intermediate layers to match those of the student, allowing direct distillation without the need for an encoding stage. The proposed method is extensively evaluated using various pairs of teacher-student architectures on CIFAR-10, CIFAR-100, and ImageNet datasets showcasing that preserving the information flow paths consistently increases the performance of the baseline KD approaches on both classification and retrieval settings. We intend to make our code publicly available.

1. Introduction

The constant effort to increase the performance of Deep Neural Networks (DNN) has resulted in deeper architectures that require massive compute power and memory to train and deploy. Also, several application settings need to deploy DNNs on hardware with limited resources, which has increased the popularity of the research field of model compression. During the past years, model compression has attracted a lot of research interest and many pertinent approaches have been proposed such as parameter pruning,

Figure 1. InDistill acts as a warmup stage (i.e., stage 1), transferring the teacher’s information flow paths to enhance the effectiveness of the subsequent main knowledge distillation process (i.e., stage 2).

quantization, low-rank factorization, and Knowledge Distillation (KD) [9, 10].

The objective of KD, one of the most effective ways for model compression [9, 15], is to transfer knowledge from a powerful network to a smaller and faster one, to extend its performance capabilities. Early KD approaches aim at transferring the teacher’s logits [18]. This enables smaller models to understand how bigger models perceive the inputs, which enhances the learning of the former based on knowledge captured by the latter. However, the lack of intermediate layer supervision impedes the learning of how the information flows through the teacher’s layers reducing the student’s generalization potential [34]. To remedy this, recent KD methods [36, 45] distill knowledge from intermediate layers, as it is empirically shown to improve the KD effectiveness.

Pruning methods are applied to reduce storage requirements or inference time [10, 25, 27]. Unstructured pruning [43] removes unimportant weights reducing the model’s storage size, while structured pruning [8, 13, 24, 26, 40] removes the less important CNN filters reducing both the model’s storage size and processing time. Furthermore, there have been efforts to combine KD and pruning for model compression, specifically [2] applies KD after pruning only to the untouched layers during the pruning phase, and [7] introduces an approach that utilizes KD for fine-tuning a pruned model. However, they do not follow the standard teacher-student setting and thus they cannot be compared with any typical KD approaches. Furthermore, pruning a teacher model to achieve architectural alignment with the student and directly distill intermediate layers has not yet been considered.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that during the training process, a neural network undergoes several phases [1]. More precisely, the first training epochs are considered responsible for the creation of the model’s information flow paths. These paths represent the routes through which information travels and is processed within the network, effectively shaping the network’s ability to learn and generalize. It is important to highlight that after their creation, these paths can only be fine-tuned through the rest of the training procedure. This critical fact has been taken into consideration by [34] to effectively distill intermediate layers, without, however, taking into consideration the increasing distillation difficulty of successive intermediate layers, from shallower to deeper network parts.

This paper introduces InDistill, a method that addresses the aforementioned limitations and can be employed as a warmup stage prior to any KD approach (see Fig. 1). Inspired by curriculum learning principles [3] and the critical learning periods of a neural network [34], InDistill suggests a simple, yet effective way to distill the teacher’s information flow paths to the student, by directly transferring knowledge from each intermediate layer separately and in ascending transferring difficulty order (i.e., from shallow to deep layers). Additionally, to expand the applicability of InDistill, channel pruning is specifically applied to the teacher’s intermediate layers when a width disparity exists between the teacher and student architectures. This selective pruning aligns the architectures, facilitating direct feature map matching and thus preserving the crucial information flow paths. Similarly, in scenarios with an extremely high capacity gap between the teacher and student models, an auxiliary teacher is also considered to facilitate the application of InDistill.

The proposed method has been evaluated on a wide range of classification and retrieval settings with the use of widely adopted benchmarks (i.e., CIFAR-10 [23], CIFAR-100 [23], and ImageNet [11]) combined with various state-

of-the-art KD approaches and is found to boost their performance in the vast majority of our conducted experiments. The main contributions of this paper are: (i) A method that introduces a curriculum learning-based training scheme considering the distillation difficulty of each layer and the critical learning periods crucial for effectively transferring the teacher’s information flow paths to the student, as a warmup step before employing any KD approach. (ii) A pruning mechanism applied in scenarios where there is a width disparity between teacher and student architectures. This mechanism aligns the architectures, facilitating direct knowledge transfer from feature maps and contributing to the preservation of the crucial information flow paths. (iii) A wide analysis involving 5 baseline KD methods and 3 widely-adopted benchmarks, demonstrating the effectiveness of InDistill in improving the performance of the baseline approaches.

2. Related work

Logits-based knowledge distillation. The increasing need of deploying machine learning models on limited-resourced hardware as well as their growing complexity has given rise to network compression [5]. KD, first proposed in [18], is an effective way for model compression by reproducing the teacher’s class probability distribution using a much faster and smaller student model. Several KD methods exploiting only the model’s output probability distributions have been proposed [12, 22, 29, 31, 32, 49]. A recent work [48] reformulates the classical KD loss into target class knowledge distillation and non-target class knowledge distillation, demonstrating the efficacy of logit distillation with this Decoupled Knowledge Distillation (DKD) methodology. The Multi-Level KD (MLKD) approach [19] enhances logit distillation through multilevel prediction alignment, by incorporating batch-level and class-level prediction alignments. Furthermore, logit standardization [38] prior to the distillation can address the mismatch in logit magnitudes between teacher and student models and thus improve the distillation effectiveness.

Features-based knowledge distillation. The first method that leverages feature maps of the teacher in order to provide the student with extra supervision is presented in [36]. This method transfers knowledge from only one intermediate layer with the aid of feature map encoding. Similarly, Probabilistic Knowledge Transfer (PKT) [33] distills knowledge from the penultimate layer’s (one layer before classification) feature maps by trying to match the teacher’s and student’s distributions of the samples’ pairwise similarities. However, transferring knowledge of one intermediate layer can not capture the critical connections between the layers. To alleviate this shortcoming, the Attention Transfer (AT) [45] proposes an attention mechanism that applies distillation to all intermediate layer representations. Simi-

larly, the Hierarchical Self-supervised Augmented Knowledge Distillation (HSAKD) [42] employs classifiers on top of all intermediate layers to supervise the KD process. In a different perspective, ReviewKD [6] introduces cross-stage connection paths in KD, emphasizing the importance of inter-level connections between teacher and student networks. Furthermore, [39] introduces Contrastive Representation Distillation (CRD) which uses a contrastive loss to distill the feature maps that derive from the last convolutional layer. [21] introduces a method to effectively encode the extracted features before KD, but still the encoding is necessary. The aforementioned methods share the same shortcomings, they disregard the preservation of information flow paths during distillation, they ignore the capacity gap between the models (i.e., difference in the number of learnable parameters), and they face the challenge of transferring knowledge from multiple layers simultaneously.

Information flow preservation. An effort to capture the information flow was made in [44] by generating a Flow of Solution Procedure (FSP) matrix that captures the relation between two successive layers. Additionally, [33] and [34] consider a loss function based on mutual information in order to transfer the information flow paths. Also, [34] suggests a critical-periods-aware weight decay (WD) scheme that reduces the learning rate of the feature-based KD after each epoch, motivated by the fact that the first training epochs are responsible for creating the information flow paths [1].

Auxiliary teacher. Mirzadeh et al. [30] suggest the usage of an auxiliary model in order to reduce the capacity gap between teacher and student models. It should be stressed though, that they do not utilize the intermediate layers during the KD. Based on the same idea, [34] makes use of an auxiliary model to alleviate the structural differences between teacher and student.

Curriculum learning Several fields have utilized curriculum learning approaches [14, 16, 20, 37, 47], which suggest splitting a hard task into sub-tasks and learning them sequentially based on difficulty order [4, 46]. In [28], a teacher-student curriculum learning framework for reinforcement learning is introduced, where the teacher determines the sub-tasks that the student should be trained on at each training step, while [35] proposes learning tasks sequentially for enhancing multi-task learning effectiveness. However, non of the existing curriculum learning approaches considers the model’s layers as sub-tasks of increasing difficulty or is designed with the aim to retain the informational flow paths.

Knowledge distillation and pruning. Finally, there have been a few attempts [2, 7] to combine KD and pruning [24] for model compression. However, neither the mixing techniques nor the approaches’ objectives coincide with ours. More specifically, [2] prunes some layers of a model

and distills the rest, while [7] applies KD on a pruned model. Instead, we prune the teacher model in order to have an equal width with the student and straightforwardly transfer knowledge from intermediate layers.

3. Methodology

3.1. Problem formulation

The problem of transferring knowledge from a teacher to a student model is formulated as follows. Let $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times h \times w}$ denote an input image with h and w height and width, respectively, $d(\cdot)$ the teacher model, and $l=1, \dots, L_d$ the layer’s index. Then, $\mathbf{T}^{(l)} = d(\mathbf{X}, l) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{d,l} \times h_{d,l} \times w_{d,l}}$ denotes the teacher’s l layer output, where $n_{d,l}$, $h_{d,l}$, and $w_{d,l}$ is its number of channels and spatial dimensions. Accordingly, consider a student model $g(\cdot)$ with θ learnable parameters, L_g layers and $\mathbf{S}^{(l)} = g(\mathbf{X}, l) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{g,l} \times h_{g,l} \times w_{g,l}}$ the l layer’s output. In addition, let $\mathbf{q}_t, \mathbf{q}_s \in \mathbb{R}^C$ be the class probability distributions of the teacher and student model, respectively, with C the number of output classes. Then, the goal of a typical logit-based KD is to match the teacher’s and student’s class probability distributions ($\mathbf{q}_t \simeq \mathbf{q}_s$). In contrast, InDistill aims to prepare the student model $g(\cdot)$ for this process by learning θ parameters that can enhance KD effectiveness.

3.2. Information flow preservation

First, let us consider the simplest scenario, where teacher and student architectures share the same width, and thus it is feasible to transfer knowledge from the corresponding feature maps directly. Specifically, the loss between models’ feature maps, $\mathbf{P}^{(l)}$ and $\mathbf{S}^{(l)}$ is defined as:

$$\mathcal{L}_{MSE}^{(l)} = \|\mathbf{P}^{(l)} - \mathbf{S}^{(l)}\|_2^2, \quad (1)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_2$ denotes the l_2 -norm. Note that InDistill can only be applied to intermediate layers.

Curriculum learning suggests dividing a hard task into sub-tasks w.r.t. their difficulty and performing training sequentially in ascending difficulty order. When trying to transfer useful information from all the teacher’s layers, one could hypothesize that transferring knowledge from shallow layers is easier than deep layers, for two reasons. First, shallow layers hold in general low-level information (e.g., edges and corners) while deep layers hold task-specific high-level information. Second, deep layers’ distillation also requires transferring the knowledge obtained by all previous layers as well as the information flow paths until then. Figure 2 exemplifies the higher loss when transferring knowledge from deeper layers, empirically validating this intuition. Given the above, we propose a curriculum learning scheme that considers the KD of each layer as a separate sub-task. Particularly, let L_g be the number of layers (i.e., sub-tasks), that

Figure 2. \mathcal{L}_{MSE} loss curves (see Eq. (1)) on CIFAR-10 (see Sec. 4.1) validation set, while transferring knowledge from 1st, 2nd, and 3rd layers.

determine the training schedule. If the total number of training epochs is E , then the number of epochs corresponding to each sub-task (i.e., layer) can be calculated as:

$$e_i = \begin{cases} a + ib & i \neq L_g \\ E - \sum_{i=1}^{L_g-1} e_i & i = L_g \end{cases}, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, L_g\}, \quad (2)$$

where parameter a indicates a threshold for each layer’s training epochs and b is a parameter that increments the number of epochs w.r.t. the sub-task’s difficulty. Also, the set of epochs that corresponds to each sub-task i is $\mathcal{S}_i = \{r_i + 1, r_i + 2, \dots, r_i + e_i\}$ where:

$$r_i = \begin{cases} 0 & i = 1 \\ \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} e_k & i > 1 \end{cases}, i \in \{1, 2, \dots, L_g\}. \quad (3)$$

By adopting the proposed curriculum learning scheme, the first $\sum_{i=1}^{L_g-1} e_i$ epochs are dedicated to the preservation of the teacher’s information flow paths. After this warmup stage, any existing KD loss can be employed, combined with a task-specific loss (e.g., Cross-Entropy loss for the classification task). In particular, the final loss is calculated as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \begin{cases} \mathcal{L}_{MSE}^{(i)} & i \neq L_g \\ \mathcal{L}_{KD}^{(i)} + \mathcal{L}_{task}^{(i)} & i = L_g \end{cases}, i \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, L_g\}, \quad (4)$$

This way, the student model can effectively form the critical connections that significantly facilitate the following KD process.

3.3. Channel pruning

In more complex KD scenarios, where there is a width disparity exists between the teacher and student networks, channel pruning is employed to force architectural alignment and thus allow for direct feature map KD (i.e., \mathcal{L}_{MSE}). The typical criterion for evaluating the importance of a filter is the l_1 -norm or l_2 -norm [17, 24, 41]. Here,

Algorithm 1 Channel pruning procedure

- 1: **Inputs:** filters \mathbf{K} and the number of filters to prune p .
 - Output:** the pruned filters $\mathbf{K}' \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times (n_o - p) \times k \times k}$.
 - 2: **procedure** PRUNE(\mathbf{K}, p)
 - 3: **for** $i \in \mathbf{K}$ **do**
 - 4: $\mathbf{s}_i \leftarrow \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} \sum_{l=1}^k \sum_{m=1}^k |\mathbf{K}_{j,i,l,m}|$
 - 5: **end for**
 - 6: $\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{x} \leftarrow \text{sort}(\mathbf{s}) \triangleright \mathbf{x}$ denotes the sorted indices array
 - 7: $\mathbf{x} \leftarrow \mathbf{x} \setminus \mathbf{x}[1:p] \quad \triangleright$ remove the first p indices
 - 8: $\mathbf{K}' \leftarrow \mathbf{K}[\mathbf{x}]$
 - 9: **return** \mathbf{K}'
 - 10: **end procedure**
-

we opt for the approach proposed in [24] that applies structured channel pruning based on l_1 -norm. Specifically, let $\mathbf{F}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times h_i \times w_i}$ denote the input features and $\mathbf{F}_o \in \mathbb{R}^{n_o \times h_o \times w_o}$ denote the output features of a layer, respectively. The layer’s kernel can be denoted by $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times n_o \times k \times k}$, where k is the kernel size. Then, we follow the pruning procedure described in Algorithm 1. Channel pruning is applied to all teacher’s intermediate layers to force architectural alignment. After applying Algorithm 1 with $p = q \cdot n_{d,l}$, the teacher’s pruned feature maps $\mathbf{P}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{g,l} \times h_{g,l} \times w_{g,l}}$ are of equal size to the student’s feature maps, which allows for direct knowledge transfer involving no encoding. Fig. 3 provides an overview of InDistill, including its pruning component.

3.4. Auxiliary teacher

In cases of teacher-student pairs with an extreme capacity gap, different number of layers $L_d \neq L_g$ or structurally different architectures (e.g., a teacher with and a student without residual connections), we follow other works [30, 34] that make use of an auxiliary model built from the teacher model using typical knowledge distillation. $f(\cdot)$ denotes the auxiliary model, L_f the number of layers (here $L_f = L_g$), and $\mathbf{A}^{(l)} = f(\mathbf{X}, l) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_{f,l} \times h_{f,l} \times w_{f,l}}$ its output feature maps. Note that $h_{f,l} = h_{g,l}$ and $w_{f,l} = w_{g,l}$ as the networks share kernel sizes. The auxiliary teacher is designed to have the same number of layers and the same number of output channels as the student, after applying pruning with pruning rate q to all intermediate layers. As a result, the auxiliary model’s feature maps sizes $n_{f,l}$ depend on the student model’s feature maps sizes $n_{g,l}$ and the pruning rate $q \in [0, 1)$, namely $n_{f,l} = \frac{n_{g,l}}{1-q}$. Having designed the auxiliary model, typical KD [18] is applied to transfer the knowledge from the teacher model to the auxiliary model.

Figure 3. Overview of InDistill. If needed, channel pruning is applied on the teacher’s intermediate layers, so that teacher and student models’ widths coincide for $l \in (1, L_g - 1)$. Then, the curriculum learning scheme suggests transferring knowledge from each layer separately, as it is depicted on the right side, where S_i denotes the layer’s i set of epochs. After applying InDistill, any knowledge distillation loss can be employed as \mathcal{L}_{KD} .

4. Experimental setup

4.1. Datasets and model architectures

The proposed method has been evaluated on three well-known datasets: CIFAR-10 [23], CIFAR-100 [23], and ImageNet [11].

Regarding the model architectures, there are three types of setups based on the capacity gap and architectural differences between teachers and students:

Small capacity gap (same width). We employ seven typical ResNet pairs that are widely used for evaluating KD methodologies (e.g., ResNet34-ResNet18, ResNet56-ResNet20, ResNet110-ResNet32, etc.). These pairs have the same width, meaning the feature maps derived from their blocks have matching dimensions.

Large capacity gap (different width). We employ ResNet50-ResNet18, ResNet32x4-ResNet32, ResNet32x2-ResNet20, and ResNet32x4-ResNet20 pairs. The teachers of these pairs have either 2 or 4 times the width of the corresponding students. In this scenario, channel pruning is applied to the teacher’s intermediate layers to match the student’s width, facilitating direct feature map KD and preserving the crucial information flow paths.

Extreme capacity gap (different architecture). Following [34], we consider ResNet18 as the teacher model (consisting of around 11 million trainable parameters) and

model	conv (#filters, #kernel)			fc (#neurons)	
CNN-A	16, 3×3	32, 3×3	64, 3×3	128	#classes
CNN-S	8, 3×3	16, 3×3	32, 3×3	64	#classes

Table 1. Auxiliary and student model architectures for CIFAR-10. Convolutional and fully connected layers are abbreviated as “conv” and “fc”, respectively.

a tiny CNN consisting of 3 convolutional layers as the student model (CNN-S). Due to the structural differences as well as the large capacity gap between teacher and student, we additionally consider an auxiliary teacher model (CNN-A). Table 1 presents the model architectures in detail. For CNN-A and CNN-S, batch normalization is applied after each convolutional layer.

4.2. Implementation details and evaluation protocol

For the CIFAR-10 dataset, the models are trained using the Adam optimizer for 60 epochs with a learning rate of 0.001 and for 10 epochs with a learning rate of 0.0001. The batch size is set to 128 and the parameters a and b are set to 2 and 1, respectively. For CIFAR-100, the models are trained for 240 epochs using the SGD optimizer with 0.9 momentum and 0.05 learning rate for the first 150 epochs, then the learning rate decays every 30 epochs by a factor of 10. The batch size is equal to 64 and the weight decay is 0.0005. For ImageNet, the models are trained for 100 epochs using the SGD optimizer with 0.9 momentum and 0.1 learning rate, while the learning rate decays every 30 epochs by a factor of 10. The batch size is equal to 256, and the weight decay is 0.0001. The parameters a and b , are set to 5 and 1, respectively.

The official train/test splits were utilized for evaluation. In the context of retrieval evaluation, the training sets were employed to create the databases. Subsequently, the test sets were used to query these databases, allowing us to measure the retrieval performance of representations. For this evaluation, we report mean Average Precision (mAP) and Precision@k (P@k), while accuracy (top-1 and top-5) is provided for the typical classification task. Finally, we also evaluate the methods w.r.t. information flow preservation. The information flow of a network can be modeled through Mutual Information (MI) [34]. MI divergence loss proposed in PKT [33] aims at minimizing the MI divergence between teacher and student, thus forcing the student model to mimic the teacher’s information flow paths. Hence, we consider it here as a measure of information flow preservation and denote it as \mathcal{L}_{MI} . The experiments were conducted using NVIDIA RTX-3060 and RTX-4090 GPUs.

4.3. Baseline methods

To evaluate InDistill’s effectiveness in enhancing the performance of baseline KD approaches we consider 5 state-

Teacher Student	WRN-40-2 WRN-40-1	WRN-40-2 WRN-16-2	ResNet56 ResNet20	ResNet110 ResNet32	ResNet110 ResNet20	ResNet32x4 ResNet8x4
KD [18]	73.54	74.92	70.66	73.08	70.67	73.33
KD+InDistill	75.09 (+1.55)	76.17 (+1.25)	72.16 (+1.50)	74.78 (+1.70)	72.29 (+1.62)	75.73 (+2.40)
PKT [33]	73.45	74.54	70.34	72.61	70.25	73.64
PKT+InDistill	73.28 (-0.17)	74.59 (+0.05)	70.36 (+0.02)	72.92 (+0.31)	70.38 (+0.13)	73.92 (+0.28)
CRD [39]	74.14	75.48	71.16	73.48	71.46	75.51
CRD+InDistill	74.22 (+0.08)	75.54 (+0.06)	71.79 (+0.63)	73.95 (+0.47)	71.85 (+0.39)	75.73 (+0.22)
DKD [48]	74.81	76.24	71.97	74.11	71.06	76.32
DKD+InDistill	75.39 (+0.58)	76.12 (-0.12)	71.95 (-0.02)	74.59 (+0.48)	71.98 (+0.92)	76.46 (+0.14)
MLKD [19]	75.35	76.63	72.19	74.11	71.89	77.08
MLKD+InDistill	75.71 (+0.36)	76.92 (+0.29)	72.64 (+0.45)	74.68 (+0.57)	72.06 (+0.17)	76.99 (-0.09)

Table 2. Top-1 accuracy on CIFAR-100.

method	top-1 acc	top-5 acc
KD [18]	71.03	90.05
KD+InDistill	71.34 (+0.31)	90.42 (+0.37)
PKT [33]	70.41	89.48
PKT+InDistill	71.13 (+0.72)	90.24 (+0.76)
CRD [39]	71.17	90.13
CRD+InDistill	71.24 (+0.07)	90.37 (+0.24)
DKD [48]	71.70	90.41
DKD+InDistill	71.87 (+0.17)	90.65 (+0.24)
MLKD [19]	71.90	90.55
MLKD+InDistill	72.03 (+0.13)	90.77 (+0.22)

Table 3. Classification evaluation on ImageNet. ResNet34 and ResNet18 are employed as teacher and student networks.

of-the-art methodologies, namely the original KD method (KD) [18], the Probabilistic Knowledge Transfer (PKT) [33], the Contrastive Representation Distillation (CRD) [39]), the Multilevel Knowledge Distillation (MLKD) [19], and the Decoupled Knowledge Distillation (DKD) [48]. Additionally, our analysis involves methods that claim to preserve the teacher’s information flow such as the Flow of Solution Procedure (FSP) [44] and the PKT-H-CR [34] methods. More details regarding the aforementioned methods can be found in Sec. 2.

5. Results

5.1. Evaluation on standard KD benchmarks

First, we evaluate InDistill on the CIFAR-100 dataset, employing the standard teacher-student pairs used for benchmarking KD methodologies. The results are sum-

marized in Tab. 2. For each teacher-student pair, we report the performance of the baselines compared to the performance of the baselines combined with the proposed InDistill method. InDistill consistently improves the performance across most methods, demonstrating significant gains. Notably, KD+InDistill shows a marked improvement in all teacher-student pairs, with the highest gain of +2.40% when WRN-32x4 is the teacher and WRN-8x4 is the student. Similarly, for CRD, the gain achieved by adding InDistill is notable, especially with a +0.63% improvement for ResNet56 to ResNet20.

Table 3 presents the results on the ImageNet dataset. The performance metrics include top-1 and top-5 accuracy for different methods, with and without the InDistill approach. The addition of InDistill yields improvements across all methods. For instance, KD+InDistill shows an increase of +0.31% in top-1 accuracy and +0.37% in top-5 accuracy. Similarly, for the top-performing method MLKD, MLKD+InDistill achieves gains of +0.13% in top-1 accuracy and +0.22% in top-5 accuracy, demonstrating the robustness and efficacy of the InDistill approach.

5.2. Evaluation on large capacity gap settings

Apart from the standard KD evaluation setups, we consider an additional teacher-student pair for CIFAR-100 and ImageNet datasets – specifically, ResNet50-ResNet18 and ResNet32x4-ResNet32, respectively – to assess the contribution of pruning in our method while the capacity (and the width) of the teacher increases. The corresponding results are presented in Tab. 4, concerning both classification and retrieval tasks. In terms of accuracy, the improvements are similar those seen in the previous experiments (i.e., Tab. 2 and Tab. 3) with gains ranging from +0.09% to +0.87%. Notably, for the retrieval task, we observe significantly higher improvements in terms

	method	mAP	P@100	top-1 acc
ImageNet	KD [18]	30.91	31.98	71.33
	KD+InDistill	31.52 (+0.61)	32.53 (+0.55)	71.54 (+0.21)
	PKT [33]	24.67	26.41	70.66
	PKT+InDistill	25.75 (+1.08)	27.46 (+1.05)	70.98 (+0.32)
	CRD [39]	25.99	27.46	70.49
	CRD+InDistill	31.10 (+5.11)	32.19 (+4.73)	71.36 (+0.87)
CIFAR-100	KD [18]	56.59	65.08	72.11
	KD+InDistill	59.79 (+3.20)	67.45 (+2.37)	72.96 (+0.85)
	PKT [33]	53.20	64.01	72.68
	PKT+InDistill	54.54 (+1.34)	64.78 (+0.77)	72.77 (+0.09)
	CRD [39]	51.34	63.19	73.70
	CRD+InDistill	58.40 (+7.06)	67.98 (+4.79)	73.97 (+0.27)

Table 4. Retrieval and classification evaluation on ImageNet and CIFAR-100. ResNet50 as a teacher and ResNet18 as a student are selected for the ImageNet dataset, while ResNet32×4 as a teacher and ResNet32 as a student are selected for the CIFAR-100 dataset.

Teacher	ResNet32	ResNet32x2	ResNet32x4	std
Student	ResNet20	ResNet20	ResNet20	
KD [18]	70.86	69.84	68.08	1.41
KD+InDistill	71.99 (+1.13)	71.65 (+1.81)	70.96 (+2.88)	0.52 (-0.89)
PKT [33]	71.12	69.94	68.66	1.23
PKT+InDistill	71.80 (+0.68)	71.92 (+1.98)	71.26 (+2.60)	0.35 (-0.88)
CRD [39]	71.41	70.62	69.72	0.85
CRD+InDistill	71.91 (+0.50)	72.24 (+1.62)	71.14 (+1.42)	0.56 (-0.29)
DKD [48]	71.16	70.22	68.47	1.37
DKD+InDistill	71.94 (+0.78)	71.95 (+1.73)	71.11 (+2.64)	0.48 (-0.89)
MLKD [19]	71.60	71.99	70.54	0.75
MLKD+InDistill	71.97 (+0.37)	72.48 (+0.49)	71.22 (+0.68)	0.63 (-0.12)

Table 5. Top-1 accuracy on CIFAR-100 for network pairs with increasing capacity gap. Std stands for the standard deviation of the top-1 accuracy for the three pairs of teacher/student architectures.

of mAP and P@100, such as +7.06% mAP¹ and +4.79% P@100 for CRD+InDistill on CIFAR100. These gains can be attributed to the preservation of information flow paths, enabling better feature learning.

While the capacity gap between teacher and student increases, such as in the model pairs ResNet32-ResNet20, ResNet32x2-ResNet20, and ResNet32x4-ResNet20, traditional KD methods often suffer from diminished performance, as evidenced by Tab. 5. In particular, the baseline approaches generally resulted in decreased top-1 accuracy across most model pairs with increasing width discrepancies. However, integrating InDistill before applying KD significantly reduces this issue. Specifically, it enhances the student’s performance notably in the ResNet32x2-ResNet20 pair compared to the wider ResNet32-ResNet20 pair in all experiments,

¹The presented values are calculated based on cosine similarity. Euclidean distance exhibits almost identical ranking results with InDistill outperforming the rest of the methods and with only a few ranking differences among them. We opt for presenting the former as it consistently provides higher scores for all methods.

	mAP	P@100	top-1 acc
Teacher	90.47	92.26	95.23
Auxiliary	66.78	75.91	82.60
Student	39.00	58.77	69.06
FSP [44]	37.66	57.41	71.14
PKT-H-CR [34]	53.00	64.06	73.33
KD [18]	39.38	58.77	73.08
KD+InDistill	42.82 (+3.44)	61.09 (+2.32)	75.17 (+2.09)
PKT [33]	51.41	62.56	73.27
PKT+InDistill	54.61 (+3.20)	65.40 (+2.84)	74.13 (+0.86)
CRD [39]	47.11	61.64	71.99
CRD+InDistill	49.57 (+2.46)	62.23 (+0.59)	73.32 (+1.33)
DKD [48]	42.82	61.11	74.45
DKD+InDistill	44.08 (+1.26)	62.18 (+1.07)	74.84 (+0.39)
MLKD [19]	43.24	61.54	73.76
MLKD+InDistill	45.40 (+2.16)	63.15 (+1.61)	74.87 (+1.11)

Table 6. Classification and retrieval evaluation on CIFAR-10.

except for KD+InDistill, and demonstrates less accuracy drop from ResNet32x2-ResNet20 to ResNet32x4-ResNet20 pairs compared to baseline approaches. This trend is reflected in the standard deviation (std) values presented in Tab. 5, where InDistill consistently demonstrates reduced std compared to the baseline approaches (ranging from -0.12 to -0.89).

5.3. Evaluation on extreme capacity gap settings

Finally, we evaluate the performance of the proposed method in scenarios where there is a need to employ a very lightweight model (e.g., simple CNNs with only a few thousand trainable parameters, as shown in Tab. 1). In such cases, an auxiliary teacher is employed to allow for applying InDistill, due to the architectural strong differences between teacher and student models. Table 6 compares the performance of InDistill with that of 5 baseline methods. The performance of the vanilla teacher, auxiliary, and student models is presented in the corresponding rows. Teacher and student baselines refer to from-scratch training without KD, while auxiliary baseline refers to performance after KD from the teacher. The proposed method consistently enhances the performance of all the core KD approaches in both retrieval and classification settings. Specifically, for the mAP metric, InDistill boosts performance significantly across methodologies, such as +3.44% for KD, +3.20% for PKT, +2.46% for CRD, +1.26% for DKD, and +2.16% for MLKD. Similarly, for the classification setting, InDistill increases the accuracy of all methods, with improvements ranging from +0.86% to +2.09%. Finally, in terms of latency the students’ mean inference time is 14.89× faster than teacher’s (i.e., 0.49ms on CPU) and in terms of storage requirements their mean size is 28KB while the teachers’ size is 42.7MB.

Figure 4. The \mathcal{L}_{MI} loss curves during KD on CIFAR-10.

method	\mathcal{L}_{MI}
FSP [44]	0.2760
PKT [33]	0.1270
PKT-H-CR [34]	0.1063
PKT+InDistill	0.0972

Table 7. The \mathcal{L}_{MI} loss on CIFAR-10.

5.4. Preserving information flow

In Fig. 4, we present the \mathcal{L}_{MI} loss curves to assess the proposed method’s capability to distill the teacher’s information flow. In particular, the loss curves of InDistill without a learning scheme (i.e., transferring knowledge from all layers simultaneously), with the WD scheme [34], and with the curriculum learning scheme, are depicted for comparison. Although InDistill without learning scheme reduces \mathcal{L}_{MI} during the first training epochs (when the critical connections are created) compared to the baseline PKT method, it impedes the learning process during the last training epochs and achieves 51.54% mAP. On the contrary, applying a learning scheme aware of the critical learning periods, such as WD and the proposed learning scheme, can successfully address this limitation. However, the proposed scheme is superior to WD, as not only is aware of the critical learning periods but it also takes into account the complexity of transferring the knowledge of multiple layers. This can also be confirmed by the mAP values being 54.61% and 53.91% for the proposed scheme and WD, respectively. Thus, we confirm that forcing the architectural alignment and being aware of the layers’ successive transferring difficulty enables the student model to mimic the teacher’s information flow effectively. Furthermore, Tab. 7 presents the \mathcal{L}_{MI} of InDistill in comparison to other methods which also aim at preserving the teacher’s flow. InDistill presents the lowest MI divergence, which showcases that it enables the student model to simulate the teacher’s information flow better.

method	top-1 acc
Baseline	69.94
Baseline+Pruning	68.64
Baseline+Curriculum	71.06
Baseline+Pruning+Curriculum	71.92

Table 8. Top-1 accuracy on CIFAR-100 with ResNet32x2/ResNet20 teacher/student pair, for InDistill’s components ablation.

5.5. Ablation study

Table 8 presents how InDistill’s components (i.e., teacher pruning and curriculum learning) cumulatively affect the student’s performance. The first row (Baseline) refers to typical KD distillation, the second row (Baseline+Pruning) refers to pruning the teacher but distilling all layers simultaneously, the third row (Baseline+Curriculum) refers to distilling the unpruned teacher’s layers using curriculum learning and the fourth row (Baseline+Pruning+Curriculum) refers to pruning the teacher and then applying curriculum learning (i.e., InDistill). The main KD method is the PKT as it is designed to be applied to the intermediate layers [34]. This makes it suitable for the Baseline+Curriculum experiment, where the main KD approach (i.e., PKT) is utilized for distilling the intermediate layers instead of MSE. Furthermore, as already demonstrated in Fig. 4, pruning contributes to the critical connections’ creation during the first training epochs, but eventually hinders the training procedure. On the contrary, pruning combined with curriculum learning enables the critical connections formation as well as the effective learning of the final task, and results in considerably enhanced student’s performance.

6. Conclusions

In this work, we introduce a curriculum learning-based training scheme that acts as a warmup step to preserve the teacher model’s information flow paths, thereby improving the effectiveness of any subsequent KD approach. Additionally, when there is a difference in the width of the teacher and student layers, we apply a pruning operation that reduces the width of the teacher’s intermediate layers to align with the student’s, enabling direct distillation. The above strategy effectively enhances the performance of many baseline methods on a wide range of retrieval and classification experiments.

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